

**Explaining and comparing the level of customer satisfaction with the quality of electronic services of public and private banks
(Case study: Tejarat Bank and Saman Bank)**

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Abstract.

Today, customer satisfaction and service quality are important factors in the success and survival of the banking sector. The purpose of the present study is to explain the level of customer satisfaction with the quality of electronic services in the dimensions of website, ATMs, mobile banking. The statistical population of this study includes all customers of Tejarat Bank and Saman Bank branches in Zanjan, and 180 people were selected as the sample size from each bank using simple random sampling. A questionnaire was used to collect information in the present study. The questionnaire used in this study is the standard e-ServoQual questionnaire. The relevant questionnaires were analyzed using SPSS software and descriptive and inferential statistics. The research findings show that there is no significant difference between customer satisfaction with the quality of electronic services of Tejarat Bank and Saman Bank, and also the difference in the average of services in the website dimension between the two banks is not significant, and in the ATM dimension, satisfaction is almost equal, but in the mobile banking dimension, the difference in the average is significant, and customer satisfaction in Saman Bank is higher than in Tejarat Bank. Also, by ranking the dimensions of electronic services of Tejarat Bank using the Friedman test, it was observed that the quality of ATMs, website, and mobile banking were respectively.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, quality of electronic services, Tejarat Bank, Saman Bank

1- Introduction

With the expansion of the banking industry and the presence of private, semi-private banks and financial institutions alongside state-owned banks and the expansion of electronic banking services, competition in this industry has become very widespread (Bravo et al., 2019). Electronic banking is providing facilities for employees to increase their speed and efficiency in providing banking services at the branch location as well as inter-branch and inter-bank processes around the world and providing hardware and software services to customers, using which they can perform their desired banking operations without the need for physical presence in the bank at any time of the day or night through safe and reliable communication channels (Shokrollahi, 2024). Today, banks consider the rate of customer attraction and retention and increasing satisfaction as one of the important criteria for measuring the quality of their work,

and this trend is increasing. On the other hand, competition among banks and credit institutions and other forms of attracting financial resources is increasing. Electronic technology is one of the effective factors in creating a competitive advantage for banks, attracting customers and their satisfaction (Ali Mohammadi, 2002). It should be said that in the competitive conditions that are expected to become more intense in business, customer orientation and maintaining their satisfaction are of great commercial importance. Therefore, banks need to create a strategic perspective on how to design and provide services in line with customer satisfaction. The most important advantage of electronic banking is increasing the level of satisfaction of bank customers, the result of this satisfaction is to improve the level of loyalty and create an effective and long-term relationship between the bank and the customer. Therefore, if banks want to increase the satisfaction of users of their electronic services, they should pay attention to their perceptions of the output, which is the quality of electronic services, and its stability over time (Hashemi, 2013). Electronic banking services are provided to customers in various forms and with specific equipment, including banking based on sales terminals, internet banking, telephone banking, banking based on ATMs, etc. (Mahmoudi, 2020).

Simultaneously with the definition of service quality, competition for its improvement and promotion has also increased, and various models have been presented for its evaluation (Shokrollahi, 2024). One of the service measurement models is the Servqual model, which was first proposed by Parasurman in 1985 and later developed by Siemens and Berry. Through this model, customers can compare the services provided by different organizations. Also, the quality of services of one organization can be measured with another. This model has been widely used to measure quality in the service sector, and different adjustments have been made for its use in different service sectors. One of the modified models that has been used to measure the quality of electronic services is the e-Servoqual model (Parasuraman et al., 2005). Today, service quality has been identified as one of the most important customer demands. Considering the increasing number of private and public banks in Iran and the privatization of public banks, and the competitive market created for service organizations, responding to market changes and meeting needs is crucial to improving customer satisfaction and creating a competitive advantage for banks. Therefore, this study aims to examine and compare customer satisfaction with different dimensions of electronic service quality in commercial and institutional banks using the e-Servoqual model.

2- Theoretical foundations of the research

2-1-Customer satisfaction:

Customer satisfaction is one of the important theoretical and empirical issues for most marketers and marketing researchers. Customer satisfaction can be considered as the essence of success in today's competitive business world. So far, different concepts of customer satisfaction have been presented, which are briefly mentioned in a few cases (Shokrollahi, 2024):

Lovelock, (2003) Customer satisfaction means that they are satisfied with the way the organization treats and provides services and the organization has been successful in attracting and retaining them. These satisfied customers, no matter how much time and money they spend for the organization, will expect high quality in receiving services.

Lingfeld, (1996) considers customer satisfaction psychologically, emotionally, which is achieved as a result of a comparison between the characteristics of the product received, the needs or desires of customers and social expectations in relation to the product. In general, according to

the study of customer behavior, every customer predicts the quality of a product or service before receiving it, using his previous knowledge. In other words, the higher the customer's expectations of the product, the higher the quality he expects to receive from that product.

2-2-Quality of Services and Quality of Electronic Services

The word quality literally means the quality, the nature, and the state of something. Therefore, when we talk about quality, we cannot limit it to the dimensions of time and space. Quality can be considered a relative and unlimited attribute that, in the current situation and due to necessity, should be paid more attention to and addressed than before (Taleghani and Taghi Zadeh, 2010). In another definition, quality has no meaning or concept except what the customer really wants. In other words, a product is of quality when it meets the customer's needs and desires (Shokrollahi, 2024).

The desire for service quality plays an important role in service industries such as insurance, banking, etc. Parasuraman and his colleagues define service quality as “a general judgment or attitude regarding the superiority of a given service” (Shokrollahi, 2024).

There are different approaches to defining quality: In the philosophical approach, quality is synonymous with inherent superiority. (Shokrollahi, 2024). In the technical approach, quality is attributed to the degree to which a product conforms to technical standards. In the customer-oriented approach, quality is a subjective matter that is determined and explained by its recipients and depends heavily on customer perceptions. This view seems to have particular appeal in the field of defining quality in the field of services (Schneider and White, 2004).

According to the definition of Christopher and his colleagues, service quality is “the ability of the organization to meet or exceed customer expectations” (Kumaro Frost, 2000: 77). Also, Kelce believes that service quality includes three dimensions: physical, situational, and behavioral. In other words, Kelce believes that service quality is a focus on what is delivered to customers, the situation in which the service is provided, and how that service is provided (Jover and Rose, 2004). In the context of banking services, service quality is defined as the customer's belief or attitude regarding the superiority of the service provided in the banking environment (Al-Hawari and Newby, 2019).

2-3-Research Background

In a study titled “Assessment of Accessibility of Banking Websites in India”, Arvinder and Diksha (2014) analyzed the accessibility status of banking websites so that the web, as an important source of information for millions of people at all levels, leads to active participation and collaboration in the social system and individuals have more and more control over their financial demands and needs. To assess the accessibility of the website, the automatic assessment tool WCAG1/0 and the WCAG2/0 guidelines are used. To further assess the reasons for accessibility barriers, the complexity score and the difference between the average accessibility errors of public and private sector banks in India were also calculated and the relationship between accessibility and the popularity and importance of the websites were examined. The results of the study showed that none of the websites studied violated the website accessibility guidelines and there was no significant difference in the accessibility of government and private sector websites in India and a framework for classifying fully accessible websites has been defined.

Asef Tafa (2023) conducted a study titled "The Impact of Electronic Banking on Customer Satisfaction in the Ethiopian Banking Industry" and concluded that most electronic banking users

are young, educated and students and working men and women do not pay serious attention to using electronic banking services, but these services have reduced customer waiting time and reduced charging costs in banks and customer satisfaction with electronic banking has increased. Ghimchiu (2022) conducted a study titled "Investigating the Use of Electronic Banking in the Ethiopian Banking Industry" and concluded that the Ethiopian banking industry faces major obstacles, including the risk of insecurity, lack of trust, lack of legality of the regulatory framework and lack of information and communication technology infrastructure, lack of internal and external competition, and to deal with it, it can use measures taken by the banking industry and the government to address various challenges. In a study titled "Measuring Customer Satisfaction with Service Quality Using the ACSI Model", Anglova (2021) concluded that in today's competitive environment, providing high-quality services is a sustainable competitive advantage and customer satisfaction has a positive effect on the profitability of an organization and leads to repeat purchases, brand loyalty. The purpose of this study is to investigate the quality of services in the Macedonian mobile telecommunications industry in order to explain to customers the perception of the quality of services provided by T-Mobile. The analysis showed that the quality of services perceived by customers is not satisfactory.

In a study titled "Investigating the Impact of Electronic Banking Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction Using the Kano Hybrid Model and Gap Analysis" conducted by Farrokhi Ostad et al. (2013), the gap between customers' expectations and perceptions of the quality of electronic services of Tejarat Bank branches in Zahedan was examined. Banks, as one of the organizations whose functions and activities are aimed at providing public benefits, are responsible for tasks such as mobilizing and distributing credits, credit operations, financial operations, buying and selling foreign exchange, transferring funds, collecting documentary claims and customer dividends, etc., which today banks can provide most of these services using electronic banking. The results of the study showed that there is a significant difference between customers' expectations from the three basic, functional and motivational dimensions of the bank and their perceptions.

In a study titled "Investigating the Effect of Electronic Service Quality Using the eServoQUAL Model on Bank Customer Satisfaction," conducted by Mokhtaran and Sharifi (2013), they investigated the effect of electronic service quality on customer satisfaction in Saman Bank branches in East Tehran and concluded that the dimensions of efficiency, completeness, availability, confidentiality, and service compensation in electronic service systems have a positive effect on customer satisfaction, and increasing each of the components will increase customer satisfaction. They also considered that correct understanding and providing fast services in line with customer needs to lead to greater satisfaction, and the existence of accurate programs and strategies for providing services to customers allows the organization to understand the real needs of customers, and with a system of accurate feedback from customers and their needs and acting on it, an effective step can be taken towards greater customer satisfaction.

Sanaiei et al. (2012) conducted a study titled "Investigating the Effect of Electronic Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention" and in this study, electronic service quality refers to customer perceptions of the quality of electronic service provided by Saman Bank's website and the ES-QUAL scale was used. Efficiency refers to the ease of use and speed of Saman Bank's website. Service performance is defined as the extent to which the website adheres to its commitments according to the promises made and performs the services correctly

and accurately. System access or system efficiency is the extent to which appropriate tasks are designed on a site. Privacy is the security and protection of information that a website provides for its customers.

3- Conceptual model of the research

According to the theoretical foundations and research background, a conceptual model for the research is presented as shown in Figure 1. In this model, the relationship between each dimension of service quality (website, ATM, mobile banking) and customer satisfaction is explained.

(Figure 1): Conceptual model of customer satisfaction
Source: (Research results)

4- Research method

This research is of the type of applied research in terms of its nature and objectives and of the descriptive-analytical type in terms of the method of data collection and analysis. Because it was conducted in a certain time interval, it is cross-sectional in terms of time horizon. In terms of spatial scope, it includes all branches of Tejarat and Saman banks in Zanjan city.

To collect information related to the background and literature of the research, as well as in formulating hypotheses and presenting the initial model, specialized articles, related theses and searching in databases on the Internet and to collect information related to answering the questions, the field method was mainly used by distributing questionnaires among the

respondents. The research variables are qualitative. For this purpose, a questionnaire is used to quantify (measure) them. To measure the variables, a standard questionnaire derived from the e-Servqual model, which is a widely used and powerful tool for measuring the quality of electronic services in service organizations, was used. The statistical population of this study includes all customers of Tejarat and Saman banks branches in Zanjan. Due to the uncertainty of the volume, the Cochran formula will be used to calculate the sample size, and the sampling method is simple random. In applied research, the closer the sample size is to the number of members, the more valid and reliable the research is, and the more confident the results can be. To determine the required sample size, the Cochran statistical formula was used as follows:

$$n = (Z^2 pq) / d^2$$

(Relation 1): Cochran statistical formula

= n Sample size

= z Standard unit normal variable value

= p is the proportion of the trait in the population.

= q is the percentage of people who lack that trait in the population (q = 1-p).

= d is the permissible error value.

Considering the error rate of 10%, the sample size for each of the branches of Tejarat and Saman banks was determined to be 180 people separately.

To examine the validity of the questionnaire, face validity was used. That is, first the questionnaire was translated and 5 experts, professors and bank experts were consulted on each question and on the evaluation of the relevant objective, and the questionnaire was approved with minor amendments.

As can be seen from Table 1, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the questionnaire is high and acceptable. Therefore, it can be concluded that the questionnaire has good reliability.

(Table 1): Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the "E-ServoQ" questionnaire

Cronbach's alpha for both banks	Cronbach's Alpha Saman Bank	Cronbach's Alpha of Tejarat Bank	Questions	Component	Questionnaire used
0/897	0/921	0/846	8-1	Mobile banking	E-Servqual Electronic Service Quality Questionnaire
0/875	0/914	0/706	18-9	ATM	
0/876	0/881	0/870	28-19	Website	
0/934	0/959	0/839	28-1		Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire

Source: Research results

5-Data analysis

5-1-Descriptive statistics of data

5-1-1-Study of gender

As we can see in Table 2, 32.2 percent of the respondents of Saman Bank are women and 67.8 percent are men. In addition, 25.6 percent of the respondents of Tejarat Bank are women and 73.9 percent are men. Also, among the total respondents, 28.9 percent are women and 70.8 percent are men.

(Table 2): Frequency distribution of gender of individuals by type of bank

Total respondents		Business		Saman		Gender
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
28.9	104	25.6	46	32.2	58	Woman
70.8	255	73.9	133	67.8	122	Man
0.3	1	0.6	1	0	0	Not answered
100	360	100	180	100	180	Plural

Source: Research results

5-1-2-Study of age variable

As can be seen in Table 3, individuals are classified into age groups of less than 20 years, 20-30, 31-40, 41-50 and more than 50 years. And the following results were obtained.

(Table 3): Frequency distribution of age of individuals by type of bank

Total respondents		Business		Saman		Gender
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
28.9	104	25.6	46	32.2	58	Woman
70.8	255	73.9	133	67.8	122	Man
0.3	1	0.6	1	0	0	Not answered
100	360	100	180	100	180	Plural

Source: Research results

5-1-3-Examination of educational qualification variable

According to Table 4, 21.1 percent of the respondents of Saman Bank have a diploma or diploma, 63.3 percent have a diploma or bachelor's degree, and 15.6 percent have a master's degree or doctorate. Also, 16.7 percent of the respondents of Tejarat Bank have a diploma or diploma, 65 percent have a diploma or bachelor's degree, and 18.3 percent have a master's degree or doctorate. In addition, 19.9 percent of the total respondents have a diploma or diploma, 64.2 percent have a diploma or bachelor's degree, and 16.9 percent have a master's degree or doctorate.

(Table 4): Frequency distribution of education of individuals by type of bank

Total respondents		Business		Saman		Age group
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
2.2	8	2.8	5	1.7	3	Less than 20 years
34.7	125	27.2	49	42.2	76	20to 30

						years
45.6	164	47.8	86	43.3	78	31to 40 years old
15.8	57	18.9	34	12.8	23	41to 50 years
1.7	6	3.3	6	0	0	More than 50 years
100	360	100	180	100	180	Plural

Source: Research Results

5-1-4- Survey of Customers with Accounts in Other Banks

According to Table 5, 89.4 percent of Saman Bank customers have accounts in banks other than Saman Bank, and 10.6 percent do not have accounts. In addition, 93.3 percent of Tejarat Bank customers have accounts in banks other than Tejarat Bank, and 9.7 percent have accounts only in Tejarat Bank. Also, among all customers, 91.4 percent have accounts in other banks, and 8.6 percent do not have accounts.

(Table 5): Frequency distribution of individuals based on having accounts in other banks

4. Total respondents		3. Business		2. Saman		1. Accounts in other banks
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
91.4	328	93.3	168	89.4	160	Yes
8.6	31	9.7	12	10.6	19	No
100	359	100	180	100	179	Plural

Source: Research Results

5-1-5- Survey of Customers Based on the Number of Visits to the Bank

. According to the data in Table 6, the frequency distribution of individuals has been determined on a daily, weekly, monthly, and annual basis.

(Table 6): Frequency distribution of customers according to the number of visits to the bank

Total respondents		Business		Saman		Visit the bank
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
19.8	71	17.3	31	22.3	40	Daily
27.4	98	22.3	40	32.4	58	Weekly
40.5	145	45.8	82	35.2	63	Monthly
12.3	44	14.5	26	10.1	18	Annual
100	358	100	179	100	179	Plural

Source: Research results

5-1-6- Investigating the first priority of customers in using electronic banking services

As can be seen in Table 7, 47.2 percent of Saman Bank customers use ATMs as their first priority, and mobile banking, website and telephone banking are the next choices, respectively. Tejarat Bank customers also choose ATMs as their first priority, and a smaller number of customers use telephone banking.

(Table 7): Frequency distribution of people with the first priority of using electronic banking services

Priority1						Electronic services
Total respondents		Business		Saman		
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
5.3	19	3.9	7	6.7	12	Bank phone
65.8	237	84.4	152	47.2	85	ATMs
8.9	32	4.4	8	13.3	24	Bank website
20	72	7.2	13	32.8	59	Mobile banking
100	360	100	180	100	180	Plural

Source: Research results

5-1-7- Investigating the third priority of customers in using electronic banking services

According to Table 9, Saman Bank customers use the website more in their third priority, and Tejarat Bank customers also use mobile banking more. In addition, in the third priority of all customers, the first choice of customers is the website, and then the telephone banking, ATMs and mobile banking are the next choices, respectively.

(Table 9): Frequency distribution of people in the third priority of using electronic banking services

Priority2						Electronic services
Total respondents		Business		Saman		
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
8.3	18	14.8	9	5.8	9	Bank phone
28.2	61	18	11	32.3	50	ATMs
23.6	51	36.1	22	18.7	29	Bank website
39.8	86	31.1	19	43.2	67	Mobile banking
100	216	100	61	100	155	Plural

Source: Research results

6-1-8- Investigating the fourth priority of customers in using electronic banking services

According to Table 10, Saman Bank customers use telephone banking more in their fourth priority, and Tejarat Bank customers also use mobile banking more. In addition, in the fourth

priority of all respondents, the first choice of customers is telephone banking, and then the website, mobile banking, and ATMs are the next choices, respectively.

(Table 10): Frequency distribution of people in the fourth priority of using electronic banking services

Priority 4						Electronic services
Total respondents		Business		Saman		
Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	
45	18	14.3	1	51.5	17	Bank phone
10	4	0	0	12.1	4	ATMs
27.5	11	28.6	2	27.3	9	Bank website
17.5	7	57.1	4	9.1	3	Mobile banking
100	40	100	7	100	33	Plural

Source: Research results

5-2- Description of central parameters and dispersion of variables

As can be seen in Table 11, the average total score of electronic service quality of Saman and Tejarat banks is 68.46, the average quality of mobile banking is 69.62, the average quality of ATMs is 69.83, and the average quality of website services is 66.22. The scores of electronic services and their dimensions are above average. And in the meantime, the average quality score of ATMs is higher than other services.

(Table 11): Central indices and dispersion of minimum and maximum scores of electronic service quality in total respondents

Maximum	At least	Elongation coefficient	Skewness coefficient	Standard deviation	Average	Electronic services
100	0	1.284	0.200-	13.99	68.46	Total service score
100	0	0.410-	0.102-	17.95	69.62	Mobile banking
100	0	0.644	0.443-	16.35	69.83	ATM
100	0	0.121	0.026-	17.26	66.22	Website

Source: Research results

6- Conclusion

The aim of this study is to measure customer satisfaction with electronic services of Tejarat and Saman banks branches in Zanjan city and compare them with each other. The sample size of this study is 360 people. The information obtained from the questionnaires collected consists of two parts. In the first part, which was presented, the characteristics of the sample under study, such as

age, gender, and level of education, are discussed. Then, in the second part, the results of the questionnaires are presented. The tests used for this study are the two-group independent T-test, the one-sample T-test, and the Friedman test. According to each of the research hypotheses, the following were examined in this study:

- Comparison of customer satisfaction of Tejarat and Saman banks with electronic services
- Examination of customer satisfaction of Tejarat Bank with electronic services
- Examination of customer satisfaction of Saman Bank with electronic services
- Ranking of Tejarat Bank's electronic services with regard to customer satisfaction

Over the past few years, the establishment of private banks has caused the public sector to face the private sector as a new competitor. In the meantime, what guarantees the survival and continuity of the activities of financial institutions in both sectors is the provision of desirable, reliable and appropriate services so that they can satisfy customers' expectations and desires, and cause their satisfaction and loyalty. This is achieved when these institutions, while paying attention to the quality of services, as a concept that includes customer expectations, strive to maintain and improve it. In this regard, banks tried to adopt new methods through the platforms that ICT provides for them to improve the quality of their services and attract customer satisfaction.

In this study, Tejarat Bank as a sample of public sector banks and Saman Bank as a sample of private sector banks were examined.

The results of the study showed that there is a significant relationship between bank electronic services and customer satisfaction.

In general, there is no significant difference between customer satisfaction of Tejarat and Saman banks in terms of the quality of electronic services in the dimensions of websites and ATMs, but in the dimension of mobile banking, this difference is significant and satisfaction with Saman Bank's electronic services is higher than that of Tejarat Bank.

The results of the study also showed that there is satisfaction with the electronic services of the website in both banks. Therefore, in order to increase customer satisfaction and achieve their goals, it is suggested to provide easy access to software related to electronic banking services, eliminate long steps in providing services and make it easier to log in to the website, update website information, create secure platforms for electronic transactions, and ensure that the website is active 24/7. Also, regarding ATMs, it is suggested to install the devices in the right place, reduce the fee charged for providing services, not provide advertisements on ATMs before presenting the password receiving page, create the possibility of transferring funds from other bank cards by ATMs, have sufficient lighting for ATMs at night, increase the number of ATMs, and provide the possibility of providing various electronic services such as purchasing plane tickets, train tickets, cinema and concert tickets, etc. to provide convenience for customers.

The results of the study also showed that the level of customer satisfaction with the dimensions of Tejarat Bank's electronic services is not the same, so that the level of customer satisfaction is prioritized by electronic banking services, ATMs, website, and mobile banking. Therefore, it is suggested that Tejarat Bank should strive to improve mobile banking and website services, instill responsibility in this bank in providing electronic services, and promote a culture of using electronic services by customers in order to satisfy its customers more.

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